

Just to Be Safe. The Transnational History of the Nuclear Energy Debate Across Media, Science, Activism and Parliamentary Debate (1950-2025)

Work in Progress Report

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Introduction

The “Just to be Safe” project seeks to study the history of the nuclear energy debate as it unfolded over time and across media, political and scientific discourses and across national boundaries. Methodologically, it is situated at the intersection between social sciences, history and digital humanities. Building on corpora of mass digitised documents, we focus on the flow of ideas between media (newspapers and radio), science (journals), politics (parliamentary proceedings), activists (popular science books, memes). Using a longitudinal and transnational approach, we analyse the evolution of anticipated futures, interpretative frames, and reference points analogue to the concepts included in book indices.

In this paper, we document our efforts to augment and scale up the traditionally manual work on frame analysis using Large Language Models (LLMs). Frame analysis describes a heterogeneous field of research practices in the social sciences and media/communication studies which “examines the selection and salience of certain aspects of an issue by exploring images, stereotypes, metaphors, actors, and messages”¹. At its core, it serves scholars to study how human interpretation and reasoning gives meaning and coherence to historical events.

For this study we revisit earlier work by Gamson and Modigliani who conducted a frame analysis of the coverage of nuclear power in US-American media based on samples of TV news, magazines, cartoons and columns in the period 1950 until the 1980s. Their study centers around the accident at Three Mile Island nuclear power plant: On March 28th 1979, the TMI-2 reactor released radioactive gas and iodine into the environment as a direct consequence of badly executed maintenance on the day before. The accident has gained notoriety due to competing alarms which contributed to misdirected efforts to remedy its consequences². To-date considered the worst nuclear accident in US history, the incident has garnered worldwide attention and led to a reevaluation of security systems for nuclear power plants. Moreover, the accident occurred in a period in which much of the initial unconditional excitement over nuclear power technologies had given way to an increasingly heated and critical debate over safety, economic viability, impacts on human health and environmental risks.

Growing resistance against nuclear power manifested itself in Switzerland as it did elsewhere in the form of organised protest against individual prospected projects (first and foremost: Kaiseraugst³) by heterogeneous groups of activists. Especially noteworthy is a popular vote from 20.5.1979: The Swiss

¹ Jörg Matthes, “What’s in a Frame? A Content Analysis of Media Framing Studies in the World’s Leading Communication Journals, 1990-2005,” *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly* 86, no. 2 (June 1, 2009): 349, <https://doi.org/10.1177/107769900908600206>.

² J. Samuel Walker, *Containing the Atom: Nuclear Regulation in a Changing Environment, 1963–1971* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1992), 211.

³ Patrick Kupper, *Atomenergie und gespaltene Gesellschaft. Die Geschichte des gescheiterten Projektes Kernkraftwerk Kaiseraugst*, 1st ed. (Chronos Verlag, 2003), <https://doi.org/10.33057/chronos.0595>.

public validated a revision of the preceding legislation which now coupled new nuclear power plant projects to actual energy needs and placed the responsibility for waste management on plant owners⁴. The Three Mile Island accident took place in the midst of campaigning by state-backed proponents and activist-backed opponents.

Gamson and Modigliani's study builds on a theoretical model developed by Gamson and Lasch⁵. The model identifies a frame as a "central organising idea for understanding events related to the issue in question". According to the authors, frames are ambivalent, evolve, overlap, may capture modestly contradictory viewpoints and exist above simple for-against dichotomies. Frames are shaped by framing devices such as metaphors and reasoning devices such as asserted roots, consequences and principles. Frames and framing devices together are conceptualised as "interpretive packages". Gamson and Modigliani identified such packages, traced their trajectories over time and related them to survey results as proxies for shifts in public opinion. Two of them, titled "runaway" and "devil's bargain" are closely related and emerge as increasingly important after the accident. They interpret "nuclear power as an inevitable, uncontrollable fact of life combined with anxiety about the unknowable disasters that may spring from it"⁶. The authors conclude that in the time after the accident "the dominant package in media discourse is fatalistic"⁷.

We hypothesize that a similar dynamic unfolded in the Swiss press, especially in light of the ongoing debate prior to the popular vote. If this was indeed the case, we expect that the "runaway" and "devil's bargain" frames dominate the press coverage.⁸

From a linguistic point of view, frames appear as subtle rhetorical devices. Their power derives from the fact that even though we can recognize frames, their presence is not made explicitly. Readers consume and oftentimes accept the frames precisely because they remain 'hidden in plain sight'. Frames provide coherence to otherwise inchoate chains of events (and sentences) thereby influencing perception of such complex issues as nuclear power.

Until now, frame analysis is a method predominantly rooted in qualitative data analysis practices which revolve around rule-based human interpretation of text. Machine learning, on the other hand, tends to rely heavily on surface structure of a text, i.e. the sequence and frequency of tokens. Detecting semantic nuances therefore posed difficulties. But with the advent of neural networks and especially the language modelling, the field has made a substantial leap forward in the automated semantic analysis of language.

In this abstract we experiment with Large Language Models as tools for 'qualitative frame analysis' at scale. The main methodological question we tackle is: to what extent can LLMs reliably detect the runaway frame (and of course others) in newspaper articles and other sources? To this end, we test different prompting and validation strategies using different ChatGPT models. Our analysis is based on a set of 9890 Swiss newspaper articles running until 2017 which were derived from the Impresso corpus.⁹

Methods

Our experiments focussed on three elements: prompting strategies, document selection, and evaluation. Prompting—often somewhat bombastically referred to as 'prompt engineering'—is the technique of writing task-specific instruction in natural language, which the model will then aim to "complete", by predicting probable continuations. We experimented with various prompts of increasing complexity, from binary to automatic 'chain-of-thought' prompting.

⁴ <https://www.bk.admin.ch/ch/d/pore/va/19790218/index.html>.

⁵ William A. Gamson and Kathryn Eilene Lasch, "The Political Culture of Social Welfare Policy," Working Paper, December 1980, <http://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/handle/2027.42/50995>.

⁶ William A. Gamson and Andre Modigliani, "Media Discourse and Public Opinion on Nuclear Power: A Constructionist Approach," *American Journal of Sociology* 95, no. 1 (1989): 27.

⁷ Gamson and Modigliani, 30.

⁸ Gamson and Modigliani, 33.

⁹ <https://impresso-project.ch/app/>.

Prompting consists of two layers or messages. The 'system' message outlines how you want to model to behave, and the contours of the task you want to implement. The 'user' message then provides the content you want to model to operate on. Our base template was the following: we provided as a system prompt the message: “You are a helpful AI that will help with detecting frames in Swiss newspaper articles.” Our user message consisted of three demarcated inputs:

We prompted ChatGPT with bullet points that correspond to the framing and reasoning devices proposed by Gamson & Modigliani. We deconstructed the “runaway” frame into the following elements:

- The "runaway" argument on nuclear power contains the following elements:
- Nuclear power is a technology that has spiraled out of human control.
- We did not fully understand what we were getting into with nuclear power.
- We are committed to nuclear power but will eventually have to pay an unknown and potentially severe price.
- Nuclear power is a powerful force that we've unleashed but can no longer control - like a genie that can't be put back in the bottle.
- Nuclear power is like Frankenstein's monster: a force turning on its creator, or a time bomb waiting to explode.
- There are invisible and delayed radiation effects and harm may not be known until years later.
- Nuclear power shows that humans have dared to play God by tampering with fundamental forces of nature.

Each prompt furthermore contained

- **A newspaper article** about nuclear energy from a Swiss newspaper written in German or French.
- **Task instructions:** the steps the model needs to follow when generating a response to the prompt.

All the prompts pose the same question— “Does the "runaway" frame appear in the article? Yes or no?”—but contain different, and increasingly complex instructions.

- **Binary:** we simply ask the model to give a yes/no answer.
- **Automatic chain-of-thought:** in this case, we close the prompt with the instruction ‘let’s think step-by-step’ which invites the language models to spend more tokens on reasoning before producing the final yes/no answer. We refer to this prompt type as Auto-CoT.
- **Automatic chain-of-thought and Quoting:** this prompting strategy closely follows Auto-CoT, with the added instruction to “support your reasoning by providing quotations from the article” (Auto-CoT+Quote).

The table below, shows examples of the completions for each prompting technique. The prompts themselves can be found in the Appendix.

binary	Auto-CoT	Auto-CoT+Quote
No.	<p>To determine if the "runaway" frame appears in the article, let's examine the elements of the frame against the article's content.</p> <p>1. Nuclear power is a technology that has spiraled out of human control. - The article discusses potential dangers and risks of the Goesgen nuclear power plant, indicating concerns about control, but it does not explicitly state that nuclear power has spiraled out of control.</p> <p>2. We did not fully understand what we were getting into with nuclear power. - The article does not explicitly mention a lack of understanding about nuclear power. It focuses on</p>	<p>To determine whether the "runaway" frame appears in the article, let's examine each element of the frame and see if it is reflected in the article.</p> <p>1. Nuclear power is a technology that has spiraled out of human control. - The article discusses the potential danger of a nuclear core meltdown and the inability to guarantee the safety of the population. This suggests that nuclear power could potentially spiral out of control. - Relevant quotation: <QUOTE>lors d'une éventuelle fusion du noyau entraînant une explosion, des éléments radio-actifs pourraient se propager à l'extérieur, dans un périmètre de plusieurs kilomètres</QUOTE>.</p> <p>2. We did not fully understand what we were getting into with nuclear power. - The article highlights concerns about the safety measures and the lack of comprehensive planning for potential disasters, indicating a lack of full understanding of the risks involved.</p>

<p>current safety concerns and the need for improvements rather than past misunderstandings.</p> <p>[...]</p> <p>Therefore, the overall presence of the "runaway" frame in the article is limited. The frame is not clearly or fully articulated in the article.</p> <p>Answer: no</p>	<p>- Relevant quotation: <QUOTE>aucun plan d'évacuation concret n'existe</QUOTE>.</p> <p>[...]</p> <p>Considering these points, the "runaway" frame is indeed present in the article. The article articulates the various elements of the frame through concerns about safety, uncontrollable risks, and the potentially severe consequences of nuclear power. Therefore, the answer is yes.</p>
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Table 1: Example of completions for different prompting strategies

To evaluate (and better understand) these prompting techniques, we pursued following strategies:

- **Manual validation:** We compare our manual annotations to the classification produced by the LLM.
- **Consistency across prompting strategies:** We inspect to what extent applying different prompts results in the same answers. Are the LLMs confident in their classification, even when applying slightly varying prompting strategies? Which articles emerge as hard to classify and are potentially ambiguous?
- **Prompt-brittleness and self-consistency:** We repeatedly apply the same prompt to the same inputs and monitor to what extent the produced answers are consistent across runs. If the prompt produces different outcomes for the same inputs, we can refer to it as brittle. In the literature, this approach is also referred to as “self-consistency”¹⁰.

For our initial experiments we used the *gpt-4o* and *gpt-4o-mini* models. We used the standard text generation parameters, except the temperature which was set to 0.7.¹¹ This allows for more diversity and randomness in the generation process. Temperature regulates the ‘creativity’ of the model, or put differently, instead of deterministically generating the same output each time, it allows the model to follow diverging paths. When predicting the next word in a sequence, increasing temperature will put more probability mass on less obvious tokens, thereby giving the model a wider variety of options to formulate an answer.

Preliminary results

Because frames are such intricate linguistic phenomena, studying them with computational instruments poses multiple challenges. To summarize the methodological aims pursued in this abstract: we investigate to what extent Large Language Models offer a valuable instrument for frame analysis at scale. In this abstract, we test the feasibility of the approach and aim to understand the extent to which these models accomplish this complex task, before applying a chosen method at a larger scale, which is the aim of future work.

We sampled articles from a keyword-based collection of more than 9890 articles mentioning nuclear power-related concepts from the Impresso corpus (as of 2024). For our initial experiments, we narrowed our focus to articles published between 1979 and 1983 that mentioned the location “Harrisburg” (TMI sample). The latter toponym serves as a proxy to find articles that mention the Three Mile Island incident. To assess historical trends we also created a set of randomly selected articles between 1975 and 1983 (random sample).

In what follows, we first explore how LLMs handle this task by looking more closely at LLM responses to articles about the TMI incident, and then ask the question about “ground truth”, i.e. assess to what extent they provide the “correct” answers (annotated sample), and lastly provide a preliminary longitudinal analysis of the runaway frame in the Swiss news reporting on nuclear energy based on the random sample.

¹⁰ Xuezhi Wang et al., “Self-Consistency Improves Chain of Thought Reasoning in Language Models” (arXiv, March 7, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.11171>.

¹¹ Wang et al.

Dataset name	Content	Explanation
Nuclear energy dataset	9890 articles	Keyword search against Impresso corpus
Three Mile Island (TMI) sample	TMI: 27 articles published in 1979 Post TMI: 41 articles published between 1980-83	Nuclear energy articles mentioning “Harrisburg”
Random sample	Pre-TMI: 200 articles between 1975-1978, TMI: 200 articles from 1979 Post-TMI: 200 article between 1980-1983	Random sample from nuclear energy dataset restricting to specific timeframes
Annotation sample	18 articles from the TMI subsample	Articles where selected based on the (dis)agreement between responses using the binary and Auto-CoT+Quote prompting strategies

Table 2: Overview of datasets used in this abstract

Given the subtlety and intricacy of the task, we initially questioned how different types of models respond. We compared the answer of *gpt-4o* (OpenAI’s “flagship” model at the time of writing) and *gpt-4o-mini* (a smaller model for more “focused” tasks), our intuition is that the models behave differently because of the difficulty and complexity of both the input data as well as the task. Our results partly confirmed this intuition. The results below are based on the TMI sample.

Figure 1: Distribution of yes(1) and no (0) answers for different prompts and models for articles in the TMI sample

What immediately captures the eye in Figure 1, is the volatility of the smaller model (*gpt-4o-mini*): it seems especially sensitive to the inclusion of quotations in the response. Just following the chain-of-thought results in largely negative answers, but after being asked to cite the original source during reasoning, the model largely switches its decision and replies “yes” in the vast majority of the cases. We observe more robust behaviour in responses of the *gpt-4o* model, while the distribution changes a bit depending on how we formulate the question, the overall direction of answers remains stable as the vast majority consist of negative answers.

Interestingly models behave similarly for simplest, binary prompts. When we don’t give the model “space” (or tokens) to reason, the distribution of the answers seems similar. Even though we turn

later to a manual evaluation, both high incidence rates of the positive cases combined with sensitivity to prompting suggest that the smaller model provides a less reliable tool for frame analysis.

Another signal in this respect is the model’s self-consistency plotted in Figure 2. Self-consistency captures the extent to which a model gives the same answers to the same question. High scores indicate high consistency, while lower scores suggest less stability, meaning the model might change its opinion when confronted with the same question.

These results indicate that the larger model tends to be more consistent, especially when we allow more space to reason. It won’t change its “mind” under the pressure of repeated questioning. What is interesting, moreover is that Figure 2 also suggests that including direct quotations tends to lower the self-consistency, i.e. that quotes can influence a model's response to go the other way. Overall, these divergences require us to rely on the unfortunately more expensive (both financially as well environmentally) *gpt-4o* for parts of our analysis.

Figure 2: self-consistency for different prompts and models for articles in the TMI sample

Of course, even when the distribution of the responses is the same, this doesn’t necessarily imply that the models agree. To what extent is there inter-annotator agreement between these models? We address this question in more detail below.

Figure 3 Heatmap comparing model output at the document level for articles in the TMI subsample

To assess to what extent these prompting strategies converge, not just on the global level but looking at the distribution of the responses, but also at the individual, document level, we consider each pair

of prompt type and model (e.g. a binary prompt processed by *gpt-4o*) as an annotator, and then compute inter annotator-agreement using Cohen’s Kappa.¹² When near zero, the Kappa scores indicate that agreement is no better than chance. Scores very close or equal to indicate near perfect agreement. The scores reported in Figure 3 suggest low to moderate agreement between most of the prompting strategies.

The preceding analysis suggests that measuring the presence of the runaway frame depends on the model and prompting technique used. Unfortunately, there is no easy way to select which strategy works best. The comparison of algorithmic responses does not tell us to what extent any of these answers are correct. For this purpose, a large part of our research consists of a manual evaluation of these ChatGPT outputs. We are only at the early stages, but we can explain how we approach the evaluation and comparison of different approaches.

For our first annotation experiment, we sampled 18 articles for manual labelling, focussing on both positive and negative examples of the runaway frame. We were especially interested in gauging whether a simple binary prompt is as reliable as the more complex chain-of-thought style prompting. For this reason, we selected cases in which both prompting strategies (dis)agreed. For example, for the cases where Auto-CoT+Quote answered ‘yes’, we selected three articles for which the binary prompt repeatedly and consistently gave positive or negative answers and cases where it was uncertain (it answered yes, one or two times out of three). We’d repeat the same sampling method for the negative Auto-CoT predictions.

Figure 5: accuracy for different prompting strategies based on the annotated sample

Figure 5 clearly indicates that in case of disagreement, the more complex prompting strategies deliver the best responses. In more than 90% of the cases, the annotator agreed with the LLM judgement based on chain-of-thought reasoning. Zooming in on the disagreement can help us establish which route leads to better answers and where things might go wrong.

However, there is a tricky problem with this evaluation, because the more elaborate completion (and thereby the LLM) has the power to convince us of its assessment. For example, looking more closely at the following argument made by *gpt-4o*, when arguing the extent to which the article reflects the claim “We did not fully understand what we were getting into with nuclear power”:

The article touches upon the argument that theoretical calculations cannot replace practical experience: <QUOTE>...les calculs théoriques ne peuvent pas complètement remplacer l’expérience pratique.</QUOTE> This implies that the full extent of nuclear power’s risks may not have been understood before its adoption.

To what extent the quote supports the claim is a qualitative, rather subjective judgment. When annotating, we experienced that the response of the LLM itself might influence our reading of the article and, therefore, the annotation. Sometimes, the response would flag passages that went unnoticed or interpreted those fragments in ways we initially understood in a different way. Rather

¹² https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.metrics.cohen_kappa_score.html

than simple hallucinations, these diverging interpretations appear to be valid, complementary interpretations in their own right and justified with the spectrum of subjectivity.

Figure 6: Probability of article containing the “runaway” frame by year based on the random sample. Figure on the left shows the results for the binary prompt, the one on the right those for the Auto-CoT+Quote prompt.

Lastly, we turn to a longitudinal analysis. We applied the binary and Auto-CoT prompt to a random sample of 600 newspaper articles between 1975 and 1983¹³ to assess changes in the presence of the runaway theme over time. Figure 6 shows the annual probability that an article on nuclear power contains the runaway frame. We applied the simple binary and the chain-of-thought prompt with quotations.

While applying these different prompts to a random set of articles on nuclear does change the timeline, somewhat, the results nonetheless point in the same direction. Most importantly, the runaway frame is not a product of the disastrous events in Harrisburg as observed by Gamson and Modigliani for their US-based analysis, but was already “in the air” in the preceding years. While these preliminary results need to go further, they do contradict the findings of Gamson and Lasch, especially because the negative frame of losing control over nuclear power, actually declines after the incidents.

	Random sample	TMI sample
pre-TMI	0.18	
TMI	0.17	0.26
post-TMI	0.07	0.31

Table 3 Probability that article contain the runaway frame based on the random and the TMI sample

However, other findings do align partly with the existing literature. We computed the presence of the runaway frame in the TMI and a random sample. We find that articles about the Three Miles Island incident are more likely to contain the runaway frame when compared to a random selection of articles on nuclear energy. Focusing on the binary prompt as an example—but the same applies to the Auto-CoT prompt—we found that the runaway frame has an incidence rate of less than 20%. Articles that report about the looming nuclear disaster in Pennsylvania, the likelihood is substantially

¹³ We divided the data into three periods: pre-Three Mile Island (1975-1978), the year of the incident (1979) and the aftermath (1980 till 1983). For each period we randomly sampled 200 articles and annotated them with gpt-4o using the binary and Auto-Cot with quote prompt.

higher, hovering between 25% and 31%. In this sense, these two phenomena do seem entangled, but our evidence suggests that existing negative frames of nuclear energy influenced the perception of the Three Mile Island incident instead of the reverse (i.e. the event changed the framing).

Conclusion and Future Work

In this presentation, we discussed a methodological experiment on automatic frame detection with Large Language Models. We focussed on evaluating how a language model responds to prompts with instructions to identify the runaway frame in Swiss newspaper articles. We showed that its responses might be substantially different and developed a few automated and manual approaches to assess the performance and behaviours of LLMs. Lastly, we demonstrated how such a frame analysis at scale might contribute to the wider historical discussion on the perception of nuclear energy, more specifically related to the influence high-profile, often disastrous, events have on the way this technology is framed.

In the future, we expand the analysis not just to more and more diverse data (e.g. books, scientific articles), but will also include other frames. More importantly, we will refine our prompting strategies as well as the automated and manual evaluation of LLMs outputs. Also, we will experiment with building smaller, more specialized language models, based on *gpt-4o* response and synthetic data. This will be crucial to apply these techniques to a large corpus of more than 160.000 articles.

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Appendix: Prompts

Below we detail the prompts used in the article. {FRAME CONTENT} contains the bullet claims of the runaway prompt as specified by Gamson and Modigliani. {ARTICLE CONTENT} refers to a newspaper article drawn from the nuclear energy data or other sample

Binary prompt

System message

You are a helpful AI that will help with detecting frames in Swiss newspaper articles.

User message

We provide you with:

(A) FRAME: a frame consisting of different claims listed as bullet points.

(B) NEWSPAPER ARTICLE: a newspaper article about nuclear energy from a Swiss newspaper written in German or French.

(C) TASK: question and description of the task you need to perform.

(A) THE FRAME: {FRAME CONTENT}

(B) NEWSPAPER ARTICLE: {ARTICLE CONTENT}

(C) TASK:

Question: Does the "runaway" frame appear in the article?

Simply answer with *****yes***** or *****no*****.

Auto-CoT prompt

Same as the binary prompt except for point (C) in the user message.

(C) TASK:

Question: Does the "runaway" frame appear in the article? Let's think step by step.

At the end, decide if the frame is present in the article by answering *****yes***** or *****no*****.

Auto-CoT+Quote prompt

Same as the binary prompt except for point (C) in the user message.

(C) TASK:

Question: Does the "runaway" frame appear in the article?

Instructions:

- Let's think step by step.
- Support your reasoning by providing quotations from the article and explain how they articulate the runaway frame.
- Quotations should follow the original language of the article and surrounded by <QUOTE> tags
- At the end, decide if the frame is present in the article by answering *****yes***** or *****no*****.